

" CHALLENGES OF INDIAN DEMOCRACY AND SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT"

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ABSTRACT

Democracy is a form of government in which the people have the power to take decisions related to governance. The essence of democracy lies in the preparation and control of the people it is a particular type of governance, a social system, a special type of economic system, a way of life, a special psychoana and a moral and spiritual ideal. The democracy of India is considered as the largest democracy in the world. However, in modern India democracy has faced a lot of challenges like: illiteracy, poverty, gender discrimination, casteism and communalism, regionalism ,corruption, criminalisation of politics and violence. This paper analyzes the challenges facing the democratic system in India and suggests reforms for establishment of a healthy and sustainable democracy in India.

Keywords : Democracy, Poverty, Casteism, Communism, Corruption.

1.INTRODUCTION

Democracy means rule of the people. Democracy is a system under which the people choose the government through free, fair and fixed term elections. We live in the era of democracy and the majority of the world's people live in the countries with a democratic system of government. Most of the countries including India have adopted the democratic setup of governance. Amongst the democratic countries, India is considered as the largest democracy in the world. The origin of the concept of democracy can be traced to ancient Greece. As a form of Government, it existed in the city- states of ancient Greece.The term 'democracy' has been derived from the two Greek words 'Demos' with means 'people' and 'Kratos'which means 'power'.Hence, democracy means the power of the people. in other words, democracy means as a system of government in which authority of the government lies with the people either directly or indirectly through a representative.

Democracy was Defined by Abraham Lincoln, the then president of USA, as "the Government of the people, by the people, and for the people". This definition has been accepted as the most appropriate definition of democracy. James Bryce, the greatest political scientist of our times, defines democracy as "Democracy is the rule of the people expressing their sovereign will through the votes".Democracy and its dimension under went changes during the period of transformation from ancient Greece to the modern world. As a result ,the pattern of democracy that prevalid in anycent Greece assumed an entirely different and new shape. In this context , Prime minister, Jawaharlal Nehru observed that "Democracy is tolerance, it is tolerance not only towards those who agree (with us) but also with those who disagree" (Nehru, 1950).Those who do not believe in democracy or have no faith in democracy follow paths of violence and intolerance. The twentieth century has witnessed a movement led by eminent scholars of political science which rejects the belief that democracy is a political concept, a way of making government decision and accepted democracy as a way of life.

However, in context Macpherson " democracy is merely a mechanism for choosing and authorising governments or in some other way getting laws and political decision made".

However, from its initial stage, the term democracy had been accepted as a political concept, but the modern world has assumed another two characteristics of democracy economic and social democracy. In a political democracy, the government is based on the consent of the people and as a system of government in which citizens of the country have a share of power. Differences in public opinion, criticism of the government are some of the elements of this democracy. In a social democracy the dignity of the human being is honoured. The democracy respects each and every section of the society as a social and human being. In this system of governance, democracy provides an ample opportunity to maintain a dignified human community. The economic democracy aims at reducing the gap between the rich and poor freedom from hunger, social security.

2.DEMOCRACY IN INDIA

After independence, India became the democratic republic on 26th January 1950 by introducing its own constitution with a Preamble. In India, the term 'Democracy' has been used for the first time in the Preamble of the constitution which is based on the concept of popular sovereignty. The framers of the Constitution of India provide a representative Parliamentary democracy in which the executive is always responsible to the legislature for its actions, policies and other works. There are three types of democracy- political democracy, social democracy and economic democracy in India. In this context it has been observed that the constitution of India aims to establish an egalitarian Society for each and every citizen to provide social, economic and political justice in a social and economic democracy. Some of the modern fundamental principles that are practiced even in Modern times are laid down in the Indian Constitution :-In democracy, people hold as the source of sovereign power and government is based on the consent of the people.

* The constitution provides certain fundamental rights to the citizens of India and it is the Supreme duty of the constitution to protect the fundamental rights of the individuals.

* Provision of special protection for those who are socially and educationally marginalized in India.

* Rule of law is the fundamental principles of the democracy and governing process established under it.

* The provision of Directive Principles of State Policy that ensure social and economic equality in India. Economic democracy is the most important aspect of democracy.

* A transparent and independent Election throughout the country with constitutional election machinery.

3.TYPES OF DEMOCRACY IN INDIA

For the first time, the direct democracy system was practiced in ancient Greece. In the system of direct democracy, the peoples of the country assemble together for the enactment of laws required for governance and they implement these rules too. Citizens were also engaged directly in the judicial process of the country. Citizens themselves used to perform these duties as per the provision of democracy. In a

nutshell, it can be said that citizens have the power to participate directly in the process of governance as well as in the decision- making process of the country. Switzerland is one of the best examples of direct democracy in the world.

Another type of democracy is indirect democracy. In this type of democracy citizens indirectly participate in the decision - making process of the country through their representatives. In the present society most of the countries of the world accepted indirect democracy as the best form of democracy because of the large size and vast populations. As this system is by the representatives, it is also known representative democracy. The country like India is the best example of indirect democracy and also considered as the largest democracy in the world. In India, due to large populations and vastness of the country, people elected their representatives at the centre, state and local levels in India.

4.CHALLENGES TO DEMOCRACY IN INDIA

CORRUPTION : - corruption in public life has been a major concern in India is the 93 least corrupt Nation out of 180 countries according to the 2023 Corruption Participation Index (CPT) reported by transparency International in fact corruption is rampant in all walks of life, be it land and property, health, education, commerce and industry. Political leaders use political power to collect and illegal wealth of the country. The tentacles of corruption have affected all organs of government including the Judiciary. corruption May have a direct impact on the economy of the country.

CRIMINALIZATION OF POLITICS : - In almost years, politicians indulge in violence and take refuge in other unhealthy, undemocratic, methods to win elections. Undoubtedly, this is not a healthy trend in politics and their is an urgent need to apply serious check on such tendencies. 2024 Election's 543 members elected in the Lok Sabha, 251(46%) have Criminal Cases registered against them Election analysis organisation - ' Association of Democratic Reforms' (ADR) has said this. This affects the functioning of Indian democracy adversely in modern india.

CASTEISM : - Casteism is an important part of Indian democracy. Cast has played a very important role in Indian society since ancient times. The democracy of India was witnessed the cast -based politics, cast -based voting patter and caste based Wars also. Casteism has also been contributing towards constitution of socio - economic inequalities. What is more alarming is the mixing of caste and politics resulting into 'politicization of caste' and 'casteization of politics' in contemporary Indian Polity which has become a grave challenge to our democracy.

ILLITERACY : - literacy is very important for the success of democracy but in India it is still a challenge to remove illiteracy. Although indian economy is one of the fastest growing economies in the world, we have a long way to go on the education front. According to the Global education report - 2004,India was ranked 106th out of 127 countries in terms of improvement in the educational sector. India has the largest illiterate population, India's contribution to the total number of illiterate people in the world is about 37%. India is one of the 10 fastest growing economies in the world, but one third of the world's illiterate people live here alone.

COMMUNALISM : - Communalism and religious fundamentalism have acquired a very dangerous form and alarming proportion in India. They disrupt the pattern of co-existence in our multi- religious society.

communalism is an affront to India's Nationalist identity and a tragic setback to its evolving secular culture. It is subversive of our democratic political stability and destroyer of our glorious heritage of Humanism and composite culture.

Necessary Conditions For The Success Of Democracy

Equal quality education for all :- democracy is obviously based on Idea of equality and the significance and necessity of education functioning of democracy was appreciated by the framers of the Indian Constitution. For the success of democracy, it is not only important for everyone to get education but also political education. Political education is an important factor that influences the political consciousness. It is the best platform where citizens have the right to know the ideas and values of democracy. Only through political education can the citizens of their country become effective leaders and advance the economic, social and political development of the country.

Political Consciousness of the People

Political consciousness is essential for the success of democracy. Political consciousness will bring awareness to citizens about participating in political work and when all the people participate in political work and then the development of the country is inevitable.

Independent Media

Media plays an important and pivotal role in convening the functioning of the government. Independent media can awaken democratic values in people. Good public opinion can be created only through independent media.

Economic and Social Security

Social and economic security is essential for the success of democracy. Without political rights it is not possible to achieve economic and social security. To ensure economic freedom for each and every section of the society, the separation of wealth amongst the few and the eradication of inequality are very much required.

The Objective of The Study

A study of the implications of democracy in the Indian system.

A study of major problems and challenges being faced by Indian democracy.

Recognise the corrective measures of improving the Indian democratic system.

IMPROVEMENT SUGGESTION

Elections are important in a democratic country because the public selects its ruling through elections. Therefore, voters should be given the knowledge of political consciousness. They should be made fully aware of their rights and privileges. For this, programs like a conference, seminar, workshop should be organised.

Proper education should be provided to the illiterate peoples of India so that they can be able to vote for the right leaders.

Media is called the fourth pillar of democracy. Therefore media should play an important role in bringing out the true

Politicians should respect that true spirit of democracy while playing their role. One should stay away from the politics of corruption and nepotism while playing his role not as a master but as a servant.

Changes should be done in peaceful, constitutional and democratic methods.

Government, NGO and peoples should collectively work for the economic development of the nation.

The legislature, executive and Judiciary should keep an eye on what is happening around us and should move forward with the world.

5.CONCLUSION:-

By the way ,India claims to be one of the largest countries in the democratic countries of the world, but the reality is that there are various challenges that act as obstacles to true functioning. But if the above suggestions are implemented, democracy in India can be very strong, transparent and public welfare. Such democracy will not only be able to protect the interest of the people of India, but will also pave the way for India's conclusive and developed nations.

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